

The Discourse of Marriage and Fertility in Postcolonial African Narratives: A Discourse Analysis

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Abstract

Marriage and fertility are recurring themes in postcolonial African literature, reflecting deep-rooted cultural expectations and social anxieties. In many societies, these concepts are closely tied to gender identity, personal worth, and communal respect. This paper explores how the discourse surrounding marriage and fertility reflects cultural ideologies and personal struggles in selected African short stories. The main aim of the study is to examine how language is used to express, reinforce, or resist social expectations regarding marriage and childbearing, particularly for women. The analysis focuses on how discourse shapes and reveals identity, power dynamics, and emotional conflict. The study adopts a discourse analysis approach, drawing on postcolonial theory and Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) to investigate the stories, *A Life in Full* by Jude Dibia, *Indigo* by Molar Wood, *Happy Ending* by Stanley Onjezani Kenani, and *Child of a Hyena* by Shadreck Chikoti. Particular attention is given to the interpersonal metafunction of language, in terms of how characters express judgment, negotiate obligations, and relate to others through speech and to how cultural ideologies are represented in dialogue, silence, and metaphor. Findings reveal that the discourse of marriage and fertility is often gendered, moralistic, and emotionally charged. Women characters are judged not only by what they do but by what they fail to do, especially about reproduction and obedience to social norms. Some characters use language strategically to resist or redefine these expectations, suggesting moments of agency within constraint. The study concludes that marriage and fertility are not merely social themes but discursive sites where cultural power is enacted and contested. Through the analysis of everyday language in fiction, the paper highlights how African writers use short stories to critique, question, and sometimes uphold traditional values.

Keywords: Marriage discourse, fertility, African short stories, gender expectations, postcolonial identity, cultural norms.

Introduction

In many African societies, marriage and fertility are not simply personal milestones but social imperatives tied to one's identity, gender roles, and communal belonging. These cultural expectations are often reflected and questioned through literature. Postcolonial African writers, particularly those working in the short story genre have continued to explore how individuals navigate the pressures of marriage and reproduction within the context of changing values, migration, and modernity.

The short story, as a concise literary form rooted in everyday experience, offers a unique space to examine these tensions. It allows authors to focus sharply on moments of personal conflict, generational tension, and social judgment. In particular, marriage and fertility often emerge as discursive battlegrounds where characters struggle between fulfilling communal roles and asserting personal agency.

The motivation for this study arises from the need to understand how discourse, both spoken and internal, is used to construct, reinforce, or resist expectations related to marriage and childbearing. While previous research has explored these themes from sociological and thematic perspectives, there is a need for a closer linguistic and discourse-oriented analysis that reveals how characters' identities and conflicts are shaped through language. This paper, therefore, investigates how selected African short stories represent the discourse of marriage and fertility, particularly in relation to gendered identity. Examining the character interactions, speech patterns, and narrative commentary will lead to uncovering how language becomes a tool for both social control and resistance. The paper, therefore, contributes to the broader understanding of how African literature reflects and challenges traditional cultural ideologies.

Marriage and fertility have remained central motifs in African literature, often functioning as markers of personal fulfillment, communal worth, and gendered identity. In postcolonial African contexts, where traditional customs interact with modern ideologies, these themes become more than narrative content, they serve as cultural signifiers and contested sites of identity. Scholars across Africa and beyond have engaged with these themes, yet there remains a need to examine how they are constructed and contested through discourse, particularly in short fiction. In African societies, marriage is often viewed as a rite of passage into adulthood and fertility as proof of womanhood and social success. As Amadiume (1997) notes, gender roles in African cultures are deeply intertwined with reproductive expectations. These ideas find literary expression in works where characters, particularly women are judged, elevated, or ridiculed based on marital and reproductive status.

Nigerian scholars such as Asabe Kabir (2019) and Okuyade (2011) have explored how literature reflects and sometimes critiques these cultural ideals. In short stories like *Indigo* and *A Life in Full*, marriage and fertility are not simply romantic concerns but socially enforced obligations, often revealed through linguistic pressure, shame, and negotiation. While the thematic relevance of marriage and fertility in African literature is well-established, fewer studies have examined how these themes are linguistically and discursively constructed. Most analyses remain focused on plot and character development without engaging closely with the language choices that convey power dynamics, social expectations, or resistance.

Ajibade and Bamiro (2017) discuss cultural alienation in African fiction but do not apply detailed discourse analysis. This paper addresses this gap by analysing how discourse dialogue, evaluative language, silence, and metaphor, construct identity and cultural tension in relation to marriage and fertility. This study is grounded in postcolonial feminist theory and Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). Postcolonial feminism, as articulated by scholars like Chandra Talpade Mohanty (1988) and Oyèrónké Oyèwùmí (1997), draws attention to the unique ways African women are positioned within cultural systems that privilege motherhood and wifeliness. These

frameworks reveal how gendered expectations are internalised or resisted in different discursive forms.

On the linguistic side, the study draws on Halliday's (2014) SFL framework, especially the interpersonal metafunction, to analyse how characters negotiate roles, obligations, and attitudes. It also integrates insights from Appraisal Theory (Martin & White, 2005), which helps explain how language encodes emotional stance and value judgment. These are key elements in narratives that deal with gender pressure and moral expectations. Discourse analysis as a method has been employed effectively in African literary studies, though more often in political or media contexts (Taiwo, 2009; Olateju, 2006). Literary discourse analysis remains relatively underutilised, especially in the analysis of short fiction. Applying SFL to selected texts such as *A Life in Full* (Dibia), *Indigo* (Wood), *Happy Ending* (Kenani), and *Child of a Hyena* (Chikoti) makes this a study that bridges methodological gap between linguistics and literature.

This paper follows the interdisciplinary path set by scholars like Simpson (2004) and Jeffries (2010), who argue that detailed textual analysis is a means to uncover deeper ideological structures. Within the Nigerian context, Onukaogu and Eyisi (2014) have emphasised the need for critical linguistic approaches in reading African literature. Dada (2023, 2024) journal articles are a response to such a call. This paper is yet another response in that direction by offering a focused, language-based analysis that maintains fidelity to both textual detail and broader cultural interpretation.

There is a growing trend in African literary criticism toward examining how social expectations around marriage and fertility intersect with gender and power. Recent works by Egbunike (2020) and Nnaemeka (2004) highlight a shift toward portraying women characters who resist or redefine traditional roles. These stories show how women navigate pressures not only in rural settings but within diasporic and urban spaces. This study contributes to this body of work by showing that such complexities are not only embedded in plot lines but also enacted through linguistic patterns, such as tone, politeness, modality, and silence.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is guided by a dual theoretical framework that integrates postcolonial feminist theory with Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). This will enable a deeper understanding of how discourse in African short stories reveals cultural expectations, gender roles, and individual resistance in relation to marriage and fertility. These frameworks are discussed as follows:

1. Postcolonial Feminist Theory

Postcolonial feminist theory deals with how women in formerly colonised societies experience gendered power relations within specific contexts of cultural tradition, colonial legacy, and modern globalisation. Scholars such as Chandra Talpade Mohanty (1988) and Oyèrónké Oyèwùmí (1997) have emphasised that African women's lives and identities cannot be understood through Western feminist lenses alone. Instead, gender must be studied in connection with local traditions, kinship systems, and expectations tied to reproduction and marriage. This perspective is particularly

relevant in African narratives where marriage and fertility are not merely private matters, but culturally sanctioned rites of passage.

The works of Amadiume (1997) and Nnaemeka (2004) highlight how women are often socially valued for their reproductive roles, while those who are unmarried or childless face stigma and marginalisation. *Indigo*, *Happy Ending*, and *Child of a Hyena* portray women with identities that are constantly shaped by these expectations. Postcolonial feminist theory helps to interpret how female characters internalise, question, or resist the discourses that define their value in relation to marriage and fertility.

2. Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL)

To analyse how these identities and cultural pressures are enacted through language, the study employs Systemic Functional Linguistics developed by M. A. K. Halliday. According to SFL, language is a resource for making meaning in social contexts. The interpersonal metafunction, which focuses on how language is used to enact social relationships, express attitudes, and negotiating power is particularly beneficial to this paper. Areas to be focused on include Modality used for expressing obligation, certainty, or doubt. Mood is used to show how speakers take positions, such as to issue commands, ask questions or make statements. Martin & White (2005) Appraisal is used to reveal emotional and evaluative language in relation to shame, pride or hope

The combination of both postcolonial feminist theory and SFL moves the paper beyond thematic analysis to investigate how power, resistance, and identity are shaped at the level of discourse. In *Indigo*, Idera's careful use of polite but distanced language reveals both her attempt to conform and her discomfort with societal expectations while *Happy Ending*, portrays the protagonist's silence and detachment as functions of discursive strategies of resistance. The combined framework enables the connection of linguistic patterns to social ideologies, and personal utterances to broader cultural structures.

Methodology

The paper adopts a qualitative discourse analysis approach to examine how language reflects and negotiates cultural expectations about marriage and fertility. The study is interpretive and textual, focusing on how discourse is used to express identity, power, and social pressure within fictional narratives in the selected African short stories. It combines critical discourse analysis techniques with literary close reading, guided by postcolonial feminist insights and Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). The methodology is designed to capture how characters' speech, thoughts, and interactions are shaped by and respond to gendered social norms, particularly in postcolonial African contexts.

The four short stories were purposively selected based on their thematic focus on gender, marriage, and fertility, infidelity and their representation of diverse African voices and social settings. They include:

- i. *Indigo* by Molara Wood (Nigeria)
- ii. *A Life in Full* by Jude Dibia (Nigeria)

- iii. *Happy Ending* by Chinelo Stanley Onjezani Kenani (Malawi)
- iv. *Child of a Hyena* by Shadreck Chikoti (Malawi)

These texts have local and diasporic contexts which allow for an exploration of how expectations surrounding marriage, infidelity and fertility vary or remain consistent across cultural spaces.

3. Analytical Tools

The selected tools for analysis from Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) are Modality and Mood types. These are used to explore obligations, certainty or doubts, and to explore how commands, questions, and declarations are used to assert power or seek compliance, respectively, about marriage and fertility. Appraisal theory examines the emotional and evaluative stance of characters, particularly in relation to fertility, shame, pride, or rejection, while silence and omission are interpreted as discursive choices that may indicate resistance or constraint, especially when characters fail or refuse to speak about their situations. These linguistic features are interpreted in compliance with postcolonial feminist theory which provides a socio-cultural lens for reading how discourse reflects patriarchal structures, cultural beliefs, and gendered resistance.

The analysis is conducted in three stages:

1. Textual immersion: This involves close readings of each story to identify segments related to marriage, fertility, gender roles, and cultural norms.
2. Discourse mapping: This is for the identification and coding of speech acts, evaluative language, modal expressions, silences, and discursive patterns.
3. Interpretation: Linking linguistic features to broader ideological meanings using the integrated theoretical framework.

Analysis and Discussion

1. Indigo – Molara Wood

Indigo is about a woman in her thirties named Idera, she returns from London to Nigeria with her husband, Jaiye whom she has been married to for five years without children. As a result, Idera becomes the target of cultural judgment, social exclusion, and internal anxiety due to her state of childlessness. The opening scene is at a baby-naming ceremony. Idera goes to congratulate the new mother, only to be shushed by an older woman *who happens to be the aunt of Bola, the mother of the newborn child*. “Congratulations”, she said to Bola Kolapo. “Shhh!” Bola’s aunt responded (p 212) *in a reprimanding tone, with a look that dismissed Idera*. This brief utterance functions as a discursive act of silencing, implying that barren women do not talk in a space where motherhood is celebrated. The woman's response which immediately sets the tone of exclusion carries deep cultural meaning signaling that fertility is the measure of womanhood, and a childless woman lacks authority or inclusion in such rites. This response also reinforces the ideological norm that excludes infertile women from communal legitimacy.

Internal Discourse and Identity Conflict

The story reveals Idera's inner thoughts as she grapples with conflicting ideas of who she is in the modern world versus what tradition expects of her. Her thoughts are full of evaluative and self-questioning language after the little quarrel between her and Bola's aunt who used the opportunity to mock Idera for not having a child. However, Idera tries to explain that it was her and her husband's decision not to have children yet. Idera could almost imagine them posing the question: what kind of woman chooses not to have a child? This rhetorical question is not directed outward but inward, showing internalised cultural pressure. The modal verb "chooses" both suggests agency and frames infertility (or delayed motherhood) as a moral and social choice, rather than a personal or medical circumstance. Idera's internal struggle highlights a key point in postcolonial feminism; that African women's reproductive choices are often subject to public scrutiny and influence rather than being purely personal.

Idera's mind went to her father's sister Yeye Koleoso who had narrated to her that she left her husband's house because she could not conceive. Yeye also metaphorically explained that a woman without a child in the society is worthless. "... *It is only a snake that crawls around without offspring behind it*" said Yeye. (213). Yeye then suggested that the traditional way is by visiting a native doctor. These inner conflicts finally brought her to a point of decision,. An hour later, herself and her aunt both arrived in front of an Ife priest. After consulting the oracle, he assures them that Idera would conceive, but all she needed to do was to visit a small village shrine near Abeokuta by herself.

This introduces the ideational dimension of discourse, which is how language reflects cultural belief systems. The following quote captures this reflection when the priest denies her access to the shrine, stating, "*The orisa cannot be consulted by a woman with a visitation in her body.*" ...*a visitation in her body* is loaded with euphemism and taboo. It refers indirectly to menstruation and reinforces the ritual exclusion of women based on reproductive biology. The impersonal structure of the sentence ("cannot be consulted") removes agency from both the priest and Idera, presenting tradition as immutable. Although Idera does not challenge the statement verbally, her later decision to bathe in the Indigo stream serves as a symbolic act of reclamation.

The act of bathing in the stream, her non-verbal resistance, represents a turning point in Idera's discursive positioning as she no longer speaks defiantly nor seek external validation. Instead, she performs a quiet act that blends belief and autonomy. The stream, associated with purification and fertility, becomes a metaphorical site of hybrid identity where modern skepticism meets traditional symbolism. This theme of cultural hybridisation is seen when back there in the foreign land Idera and her husband were influenced into living the lifestyle and practices of the culture of the people they lived among but now back in Nigeria the cultural values of the African society got the better of them and they again succumbed.

When Idera later discovers that she is pregnant, she names the child "Indigo," thus completing a discursive circle. She moves from being silenced to naming; from being marginalised to symbolic participation. This naming act, therefore, serves as a speech act of self-restoration, leading to reconciliation with cultural roots, on her own terms.

In sum, the discursive pattern in Indigo begins with silencing and exclusion enacted through brief, directive language that reflects cultural norms. Internal conflict is expressed through rhetorical

questions, modality, and evaluative language, revealing identity tension while religious and traditional authority are framed in impersonal, absolute language that reinforces gendered exclusion. Resistance takes the form of silent or symbolic acts rather than direct confrontation while the final act of naming restores voice and agency, blending tradition and personal choice. The next section is the analysis of *A Life in Full*.

2. A Life in Full – Jude Dibia

A Life in Full by Jude Dibia explores the theme of marriage as a cultural obligation, particularly for men. It exposes how discourse functions as a means of enforcing conformity. The story focuses on Victor, a successful but unmarried man who lives in Lagos. He is under pressure from his mother, Mabel, to marry and have children. Through their dialogues, silence, and indirect speech, Dibia presents a firm critique of how cultural expectations about marriage are discursively imposed and resisted. In the dialogue between mother and son, Mabel's speech is dominated by declarative statements and emotionally charged appeals which reflect her internalisation of communal expectations. She says, "*You are the first son. You have a responsibility to the family.*"

This statement reveals several discursive features. First, the use of the second-person address "you" places the burden directly on Victor and the phrase "have a responsibility" is a moral imperative and obligation, that negates personal suggestion. This is an example of the language of duty which is rooted in patriarchal family structures that prioritise lineage and inheritance. Through this kind of language, Victor's mum invokes birth order and familial expectation, by linking masculinity with the ability to marry and reproduce. In her discourse, she frames marriage not as an individual decision, but as a societal expectation, particularly for first-born sons.

On the other hand, Victor's responses are marked by interrogative mood and defiant tone. His rhetorical question resists the normative assumption embedded in his mother's worldview "*Must I marry just because others do?*". His use of "must", a strong modal of obligation, is strategic as it echoes the expectation and then turns it into a question. This speech act functions as discursive resistance, challenging tradition in its own logic. Victor also frequently uses short, assertive statements such as "*I like my life the way it is.*" "*I won't discuss this again.*" These statements reflect a deliberate withdrawal from the cultural narrative. He asserts personal autonomy over social compliance through his language by drawing from modern, individualistic ideology. His need to repeatedly defend his choice suggests that his identity is not fully settled. It is being contested through every interaction with his mother.

Victor is also uncomfortable with his mother's presence in his apartment. However, this is not always directly expressed. Instead, it is exhibited through silence, awkwardness, and non-verbal cues. He makes it clear that her visits disrupt his "personal space." The story uses spatial metaphors like "his space," "don't touch that" as a discourse strategy to highlight the tension between individual privacy and communal obligation. This silence and spatial distancing represent another form of discursive resistance very much unlike open confrontation. Withholding speech, therefore, becomes a tool of power, a refusal to engage in the expected script of compliance.

No amount of blackmail from his mother could bring about compliance. Mabel says. "*People are laughing at me. They say I must have done something wrong.*" With a statement like this she tries

to shift the burden of shame from Victor to herself through the use of reported speech (“they say”), thereby constructing an invisible community whose judgment is constant and inescapable. This aligns with the communitarian ethos in many African cultures, where individual actions rub off on the entire family. Rather than issuing direct commands, she applies the discourse of indirect coercion to appeal to Victor’s sense of familial loyalty and fear of public ridicule.

In summary, the discursive patterns in *A Life in Full*, are captured through Mabel’s discourse of using declaratives, emotional appeals, and third-party judgment to pressure Victor. On the other hand, Victor’s language centres on resistance, using rhetorical questions, short assertions, and references to personal space to reject expectations. Silence and avoidance function as strategies of disengagement, signaling discomfort without confrontation. Overall, the story reflects how marriage expectations for men are equally tied to cultural constructions of identity and responsibility. The third short story *Happy Ending* is analysed next.

3. Happy Ending – Stanley Onjezani Kenani

Happy Ending by Stanley Onjezani Kenani offers a subversive exploration of the tensions surrounding marriage, fertility, masculinity, and shame within African cultural frameworks. The story centres on Dama and his wife Tithlepo. Dama finds a love letter in his wife's handwriting with no name or address and accuses his wife of infidelity. Through a layered narrative of suspicion, betrayal, and ritual, the story exposes how deeply embedded socio-cultural discourses influence moral choices and emotional outcomes. The ideational metafunction, which deals with how language represents reality, is foregrounded through transitivity choices that highlight social roles, power, and culpability. Characters are constructed through material processes. In the following expressions, “*He sought the help of a spiritualist...*”, “*She forced Abisalomu...*”, the verbs position Dama and Tithlepo as agents of consequential actions, revealing how cultural expectations such as the need for children in a marriage can translate into extreme and morally fraught decisions.

Tithlepo’s coercion of Abisalomu, for instance, is not simply a personal act, but one shaped by institutionalised gendered pressure to fulfill reproductive roles. The mental and verbal processes also reveal internal conflict and emotional inheritance; “*Dama had remained chaste and was afraid...*”, “*He told himself after his father's death that he would not die like his father.*” These constructions externalise Dama’s inner life, showing how shame is not only socially imposed, but also personally internalised, passed down from father to son. Such linguistic patterns foreground the intergenerational discourse of moral burden and the need for redemption through marital stability. The interpersonal metafunction, concerned with expressing relationships and attitudes, is powerfully evident through Appraisal Theory.

Kenani uses Judgment, that is evaluative language about character and behaviour to signal moral alignment. “*His father, a shameless womaniser...*” “*She forced Abisalomu....*” These negative judgments reflect societal values concerning sexual morality, fidelity, and agency. Dama’s chaste behaviour is framed as virtuous and disciplined, a conscious departure from his father’s legacy, while Tithlepo’s actions, though motivated by loyalty, are cast in the shadow of transgression. After the whole story had unfolded, we see Affect strongly displayed representing emotion discursively: “*Between them lay an uneasy coldness.*” Shame and emotional withdrawal are conveyed in this expression, not through overt speech but through evaluative silence, indicating

the psychological costs of marital failure and reproductive anxiety. The modal verb “lay” in a circumstantial clause gives weight to the emotional void, representing a passive but persistent rupture.

Further engagement strategies such as reporting speech through others heighten the moral tension without direct confrontation; “*She told her friend she had forced Abisalomu... she was doing it for Dama.*” This layering of voice, a key feature of heteroglossia, allows the narrative to present multiple moral viewpoints, underscoring the complex discursive dynamics of guilt, justification, and gendered sacrifice.

The textual metafunction, which organizes the flow of information, is equally significant. The story’s thematic structure repeatedly places Dama at the start of narrative clauses, emphasising his centrality: “*Dama finds a love letter in his wife’s handwriting...*”, “*Dama ran to the old Simbazako...*”. This recurrent pattern reflects a worldview in which masculine control and experience dominate the narrative field, even as the character himself struggles with a loss of authority. Moreover, the story’s cohesion relies on the repeated invocation of key terms—*shame, father, gossip, childlessness*—which function as lexical chains to reinforce the emotional and cultural weight of fertility within marriage.

The ending phrase, “*Between them lay an uneasy coldness.*” demonstrates textual metaphor, conveying emotional rupture with syntactic simplicity. The structure finalises the tragedy not with confrontation or clarity but with discursive absence, an echo of unresolved trauma and broken communication. Silence, here, functions not as peace but as social paralysis. The story constructs a world where fertility is not only biological but ideological, and where marital success is measured against community standards and ancestral shame. Characters negotiate these pressures through speech, silence, coercion, and ritual, all filtered through a discursive economy of judgment, fear, and suppressed affect.

The story shows that in the African postcolonial context, marriage is not merely a private union but a socially policed institution, one where language plays a central role in defining legitimacy, enforcing norms, and processing moral transgressions. By embedding these meanings within his characters’ speech, thoughts, and silences, Kenani crafts a narrative where discourse itself becomes the site of struggle, resistance, and tragic irony. The next section analyses the short story, the *Child of a Hyena*.

4. Child of a Hyena – Shadreck Chikoti

Child of a Hyena by Shadreck Chikoti presents a vivid and symbolic portrayal of how cultural myths and societal discourse are used to explain and enforce gender norms, particularly in relation to childbearing. It is a hauntingly introspective narrative that interrogates how deeply fertility rituals, paternity, and shame are discursively embedded in the fabric of traditional African society. The story is set between Denmark and Malawi. Phereni, the protagonist, is a diasporic African whose confrontation with his roots compels a painful reckoning with the truth of his biological origins. The story offers a discursive space to explore how language carries not only emotion but also cultural trauma.

Phereni's father, Bwande adopted the *fisi* or hyena custom, a Malawian cultural practice in which a man is designated (paid) to impregnate a woman if her husband is believed to be infertile. The practice is deeply patriarchal and shrouded in secrecy, constructed through euphemistic language that masks its ethical ambiguity. Phereni learns, after many years, that the man he had always known as his father, Bwande, was not his biological father; rather, it was Saide, a village polygamist and drunkard, who was chosen to perform the ritual.

The psychological rupture this causes in Phereni is intense and complex as reflected in his words to his wife "*I am the child of a hyena, Mathilda. Saide is my father.*" This simple declarative clause carries the weight of cultural betrayal and personal shame. The ideational metafunction here captures the stark reality of biological fact clashing with emotional truth. Saide is described through appraising terms such as "drunkard" and "polygamist" thus, embodying the contradictions of African masculinity both necessary to the system and morally compromised within it.

Throughout the story, Phereni is engaged in an interpersonal negotiation of identity, particularly with his Danish wife, Mathilda. The tension between them is not one of marital conflict, but of cultural incomprehensibility. Phereni cannot bring himself to reveal the truth of his origins, not only because of shame, but because the discourse around the *fisi* custom is untranslatable in Western moral frames. When he finally explains to Mathilda the hyena custom, it is through emotional trauma which marks a moment of linguistic and emotional release. This act reveals affect (distress, shame) and judgment (cultural critique, self-condemnation). Phereni evaluates not only his father's act, but the entire system that sanctioned it, using the metaphor of the hyena, an animal culturally associated with greed, lust, and darkness. It is an animal often also associated with unpredictability, deviance, and barrenness in African folklore. All these representations are the reasons behind the trauma Phereni suffers.

The textual metafunction of the story is organised around fragmentation, flashback, and silence. Much of the narrative tension builds on what is withheld, such as Phereni's reluctance to speak, the unanswered questions about his past, and the community gossip that surrounds his birth. The story's structure reflects a disrupted thematic progression, mirroring Phereni's fragmented identity and psychological dislocation.

There are binary discourses which collide in the protagonist's world, that is, Denmark and Malawi, modernity and tradition, marriage and betrayal, making it impossible for him to find peace without confronting both personal and cultural histories. Phereni like Victor (*A life in full*) chose not to have children even though unlike Victor he is married. He is also caught in the hybrid world of mixed cultures. His refusal to return to Africa is more than physical reluctance; it is a discursive resistance to being named, to being associated with a practice that strips identity from its subjects in the name of tradition. "*He never wants to go back to Africa... because it makes him forget some things in his life.*" (p. 96) This use of metaphorical language indicates that the return is not just geographic but symbolic. It is a return to cultural shame, a space where his sense of self collapses under ancestral obligation.

In this narrative, Chikoti draws attention to how fertility is not only a biological concern in African contexts, but a site of ideological power and social engineering. The *fisi* custom is portrayed not through sensationalism, but through a discourse of melancholy and ritualised trauma. Phereni's

pain is not solely that of illegitimacy, but of being made a product of a discourse he had no voice in. “*Child of a Hyena*” demonstrates that the discourse of fertility in African cultures is inseparable from themes of paternity, secrecy, gendered expectation, and ancestral shame. Using Halliday’s metafunctions, we see that the story operates on multiple semiotic levels, representing hidden experiences, negotiating fractured relationships, and structuring narrative silences.

Through Phereni, Chikoti illustrates how one’s biological origins, when steeped in cultural taboo, can unsettle both personal identity and marital harmony. The story ultimately challenges the legitimacy of practices like the *fisi* custom, not by condemning them directly, but by exposing the emotional and moral residue they leave on those born of their logic. Through direct, metaphorical, and withheld language, Chikoti offers a meditation on the cost of upholding tradition at the expense of truth and autonomy.

Comparative Discussion

The four short stories analysed in this study together present a compelling interrogation of how marriage and fertility are discursively constructed, culturally policed, and emotionally internalised in postcolonial African societies. Through distinct characters, locations, and cultural pressures, these stories illuminate the nuanced ways in which gender, sexuality, and reproductive expectation shape personal identity and relational dynamics. What binds these narratives is the central role of discourse, whether spoken, underlining, or silenced in shaping the characters’ experiences and choices. Language is a tool of cultural enforcement across all stories. In *Indigo* and *A Life in Full*, older family members and community figures speak in declaratives, imperatives, and culturally sanctioned idioms to express expectation and disappointment.

In *Indigo*, Molar Wood offers a poignant portrayal of a woman marginalised due to her childlessness. The protagonist, Idera, is excluded from family rituals and spiritual communion because of her reproductive status. Through metaphor, gesture, and suppressed speech, the story constructs fertility as both a social expectation and a gatekeeper to inclusion, especially within female communal spaces. Her final act of bathing in the forbidden stream becomes a symbolic resistance, an attempt to reclaim dignity from a discourse that deems her spiritually deficient.

Jude Dibia’s *A Life in Full* centres on a man trapped within societal scripts of masculinity and marriage. The protagonist, Victor, openly refuses marriage and asserts his personal space, seeing his unmarried status as non-existential condemnation. He resists expectations through assertive speech and rhetorical questions. In *Happy Ending*, Stanley Onjezani Kenani turns the spotlight on male vulnerability and moral anxiety. Dama’s childlessness, coupled with his determination not to be like his father sets the stage for ritual revenge, marital surveillance, and emotional collapse. The spiritualist’s grotesque language of vengeance and the tragic outcome of Tithelapo’s coerced pregnancy show how fertility discourse can engender both moral inversion and intimate devastation. The story’s ending, laden with silence and unresolved guilt underscores the emotional paralysis induced by a culture that demands fertility at any cost.

In *Child of a Hyena*, Shadreck Chikoti explores intergenerational trauma and identity fracture resulting from traditional fertility customs. Phereni, born of the *fisi* ritual, lives with the psychological weight of being “the child of a hyena.” His refusal to return to Malawi, and his

difficulty explaining this to his Danish wife, reflect how language fails in cross-cultural contexts to fully express shame rooted in tradition. His eventual confession to Mathilda represents both emotional release and a discursive reclaiming of his own history.

Across the stories we see the asymmetry of discursive burden between men and women. In *Indigo (Idera)*, *Happy Ending (Tithelepo)*, and *Child of a Hyena (Phereni's mother)*, women bear the weight of infertility, whether they are medically responsible, or not. Their worth is judged through communal language, metaphor, or silence. This disparity reflects deeply gendered cultural scripts, where female identity is more tightly tethered to biological and marital roles. The discourse surrounding women's bodies is more prescriptive, emotional, and moralistic, while male resistance is often framed in the language of freedom or individuality.

Shame operates discursively in all the stories, whether through open rebuke (as in *Indigo*), sarcastic naming (as in *Child of a Hyena*), or veiled blame (as in *Happy Ending*). In each case, language becomes a carrier of stigma, sometimes more powerful than action itself. The repetition of the phrase "child of a hyena" shows how lexical fixation can trap individuals in inherited identities. The communal use of proverbs, euphemisms, and metaphors helps naturalise these gendered roles, making them appear culturally inevitable rather than ideologically constructed.

All four stories demonstrate that identity is formed and contested through discourse, not simply assigned. Whether through speech, silence, inner thought, or symbolic acts, characters attempt to reframe, resist or accept the roles that culture has prescribed for them. In these moments, discourse becomes a tool of liberation, as well as a mechanism of control. Taken together, these stories demonstrate that the discourse of marriage and fertility in African fiction is anything but monolithic. Each narrative exposes the emotional violence that underlies seemingly normalised practices, from spiritual exile and marital silencing to cultural secrecy. While the protagonists respond differently; some with rebellion, others with resignation, all are forced to negotiate selfhood through the lenses of cultural expectation and gendered scripts. Across these stories, discourse operates not just as communication but as a cultural battleground, where voice, silence, naming, and metaphor encode both pain and resistance.

Conclusion

The paper has critically examined how marriage and fertility are represented as contested discourses in four postcolonial African short stories. Through the application of Systemic Functional Linguistics and Appraisal Theory, the analysis has shown that these narratives use language, silence, metaphor, and affect to articulate the deep tensions between tradition, identity, and personal agency.

Molara Wood's *Indigo* illustrates how ritual exclusion and bodily judgment operate within matriarchal spaces, while Jude Dibia's *A Life in Full* reveals the theme of marriage as a cultural obligation, particularly for men. Stanley Onjezani Kenani's *Happy Ending* interrogates how cultural pressure, and reproductive anxiety can lead to moral compromise and marital disintegration, and Shadreck Chikoti's *Child of a Hyena* confronts the psychological residue of fertility rituals, revealing how personal shame can transcend generations and geographies.

Together, these stories provide a multifaceted lens into the discourse of fertility in African contexts. They reveal how reproductive expectation becomes a mechanism of social control, how masculinity and femininity are linguistically shaped by success or failure to procreate, and how silence is often the only available resistance in spaces where speech threatens social collapse.

By analysing these texts through discourse-based frameworks, the paper affirms the role of African fiction as both a mirror of cultural anxiety and a tool for cultural critique. The characters in these stories may not escape their cultural scripts, but through the language of fiction, their stories interrupt and question the very ideologies that bind them.

In conclusion, this research contributes to African literary studies by highlighting the role of discourse in representing gender, power, and social change. It affirms that postcolonial African fiction, especially in its shorter forms remains a vital space for interrogating tradition and imagining alternative ways of being.

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